

Digital Twins for Data Centre Cooling Optimisation and Waste Heat Recovery

Sara Giordani, Rossano Scoccia^(✉), and Marcello Aprile

Department of Energy, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy
rossano.scoccia@polimi.it

Abstract. The paper explores the development of a Digital Twin (DT) for the management and optimisation of heat recovery in data centres, using HYCOOL-IT project demo site. The project features the development of a “Building Digital Twin Environment” as a “Platform as a Service”, integrating SIMBOT-based interactive simulators and Web API microservices to support processes from planning to performance evaluation. The article describes the integration of a waste heat recovery system within the data centre Z3 to heat the adjacent university building BL26. The DT architecture incorporates real-time data processing and a Software-in-the-Loop Model Predictive Control system to optimise control actions. Two DTs are under development: the data centre DT and the active heat recovery system DT. The former will optimise performance by continuously monitoring and controlling data centre conditions, cooling system settings, and power supply system. Simulations of the server room, chillers, and power systems will enable testing of management strategies for use cases like free cooling and emission subsystem operation optimisation. The latter will monitor the integration of a water-water heat pump (WW-HP) with the BL26 heating system, tracking electricity use, water temperatures, and flow rates. Control strategies will adjust setpoints, operation modes, and flow or temperature differences to improve system efficiency. Dynamic simulations could assess BL26 heating demand and WW-HP. Use cases include integrating WW-HP into the current plant, optimising mid-season operation, and implementing free cooling strategies to enhance energy efficiency.

Keywords: Digital Twin · Data Centre · Waste Heat Recovery · Energy Efficiency · Heat pump · BDTE · PaaS · MPC · SiL

1 Introduction

The concept of the Digital Twin (DT) was first introduced in 2002 by Michael Grieves at the University of Michigan in the context of Product Lifecycle Management. The proposed model comprised three key components: a real space, a virtual space, the link for data flow from real space to virtual space and the link for information flow from virtual space to real space [1].

Although several authors and researchers have attempted to define the concept of DT for the construction sector, currently there is no universally accepted definition of the term [2]. Recently, a paper [3] has derived the definition of Digital Twin in the built

environment from over 15,000 scientific publications, highlighting significant variations in definitions based on applications domains. A DT is often described as a continuously updated virtual replica of a physical entity [4]. The connection between the virtual-physical duality is provided by data in its various forms [5]. The way this data circulate between digital models and physical components is one of the key points of DT definition. Some consider a digital model to be a DT if it incorporates real-time data, enabling continuous monitoring of the physical entity actual operation. Others, however, believe that a system can only be considered a DT if it captures and streams data to a digital platform that performs real-time analysis to optimise the design and the performance [6]. In this view, real-time data must be processed to generate feedback that enhances the management and operation of the physical entity. Hence, application of DT includes real-time monitoring, designing/planning, optimisation, maintenance, remote access, etc. [7]. Data flow between the digital and physical twins are continuously updated and adapted to the changes in the physical asset – supported by technologies such as AI, machine learning, sensors and IoT. This allows sharing insights, supporting decision-making, and enabling simulation, prediction, monitoring, control, and performance optimisation of the physical asset throughout its lifecycle [8]. In the case of bidirectional information exchange, a crucial point of discussion is how data is transmitted from the digital model to the physical entity. Data transmission can either be fully automated within the virtual-physical loop or involve a human intermediary who evaluates whether to implement the changes suggested by the optimisation process. A committee is currently drafting a standard [9] for this approach, and we are aligning our work with their proposed definitions: “Digital representation of a target entity with data connections that enable convergence between the physical and digital states at an appropriate rate of synchronization. Digital twin has some or all the capabilities of visualization, simulation, surveying, monitoring, forecasting, control, etc.”.

DTs have the potential to significantly enhance the Operation and Maintenance (O&M) phase of building assets [10]. They enable more efficient use of O&M data, improve the perception and visualisation of building systems, and facilitate automated feedback control [11]. DT-based anomaly detection process allows for continuous monitoring of building components, thereby enhancing automated asset monitoring during the O&M phase [12]. DT technologies also support more efficient and responsive Facility Management (FM) planning and control by providing real-time status updates of building assets, ultimately improving the performance of MEP systems throughout the O&M phase [13]. However, challenges remain in real-time decision-making, data interoperability, and predictive analytics, highlighting the need to bridge the gap between theoretical advancements and practical, real-world applications [14].

Despite these promising capabilities, several challenges still hinder the widespread adoption of DT solutions. Many of these challenges stem from the novelty of the technology, resulting in a lack of standards and regulations, a shortage of competent engineers and technicians, and limited availability of supporting software [7]. Additionally, the effective deployment of DT solutions depends heavily on robust data acquisition systems and their integration with Building Management Systems (BMS), which often requires specialized engineering expertise [15]. Moreover, the quality of collected data – serving as input for analyses and simulations on the DT virtual entity – remains critical to ensure

the accuracy and reliability of the results [16]. Nevertheless, despite these barriers, the integration of DT technologies continues to expand, particularly in the domains of thermal comfort and energy management for buildings, with an increasing number of studies focusing on thermal comfort monitoring, visualization, tracking, energy management, prediction, and optimization for existing buildings [17].

This paper concerns the DT applications for a data centre and its waste heat recovery system. Waste Heat Recovery (WHR) technology is considered as a promising approach to improve energy efficiency, achieve energy and energy cost savings, and mitigate environmental impacts [18]. The DT environment is implemented using the IDP [19] platform, which facilitates the connection of physical devices to the cloud, allowing data collection and real time access.

2 Case Study Description

2.1 HYCOOL-IT Project

HYCOOL-IT is a three-year research and innovation initiative currently in its 16th month, bringing together nine partners from six European countries. The main objective is to develop processes supported by innovative solutions, both digital and technical, for the efficient and reliable implementation of IT server rooms in advanced tertiary buildings, with a particular focus on replicability through standardization. HYCOOL-IT includes the creation of a Building Digital Twin Environment (BDTE), developed as a Platform as a Service (PaaS), with specific Web API microservices to connect dedicated tools supporting planning, design assessment, commissioning, and performance evaluation. This includes the so called SIMBOTs to facilitate the effective integration and operation of these advanced server rooms within buildings. A SIMBOT is an open-source, semantically structured representation – or a corresponding library component within a simulation environment – of the mathematical model of a commercial equipment. Built using standardised library components, mathematical functions, fluid dynamics, and interface ports, the model is designed for real-time execution and aligns with the manufacturer's performance specifications. The implementation could be done using FMI standard [20]. Moreover, SIMBOTs pave the way for the future prescription of the innovative technical equipment proposed in the project. In addition, existing rooms can be mirrored and enhanced with the usage of BDTE to generate improved baselines and forecasting, supporting designers in the design phase by helping them choose the best design option. Maintenance engineers can also leverage BDTE to enable performance contracting and ensure the realization of key performance indicators (KPIs).

All methodology and software solutions will be tested and validated in the Bovisa Campus at the Z3 data centre, undergoing renovation, serving as a representative TRL 5 Living Lab. This paper will show the analysis conducted on the Z3 data centre and the WHR system designed to recover heat from the server room to heat up the adjacent building. It will also discuss the potential benefits of developing a DT for both the data centre and the heat recovery system.

2.2 Data Centre Z3

“Z3” is the nickname of the data centre of the University Politecnico di Milano completed in 2013. It is a small data centre with a net climatized area of around 150 m². The cooling load in the starting phase was around 80 kW. The forecasted cooling load at maximum expansion is 320 kW. The current cooling load is 190 kW. The servers are installed in four rows of racks and grouped in two HAC (Hot-Aisle Containment) islands. One HAC island is for university administrative services, while the other is for High Performance Computing (HPC). Figure 1 displays the schematic floor plan of Z3 data centre, complete with description of the various components and zones.

Fig. 1. Z3 data centre schematic floor plan.

The Z3 cooling plant is composed of two chillers, two cooling distribution units (CDUs) and twelve InRow Half Rack RC terminals (“InRow cooling units” from now on), they are a kind of fan-coil cooling emission sub-system. The indoor part of the data centre is divided in three spaces: the server room, the battery room, and the electric panels room. The server room hosts the server racks, the InRow cooling units, the CDUs and the uninterruptible power supply units (UPSs). The outdoor part of the data centre hosts the two chillers, the water storage tank, and the electrical generator.

To ensure cooling plant redundancy, the chillers operate alternately. An energy audit is conducted on the data centre Z3, revealing that the cooling system is not working

efficiently. In fact, the Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) is lower than expected. During warmer months is just around 1.75, while it increases to approximately 2.9 during colder months. The heat produced by the servers is captured by the InRow cooling units, which re-emit cooled air into the room.

Currently, the heat produced by the servers and balanced by the InRow cooling units is dissipated without any recovery. Therefore, a system that can recover the heat produced by the servers to heat an adjacent building is designed.

2.3 Waste Heat Recovery System

Two buildings of the Bovisa campus, located near the data centre, are analysed to determine the most suitable location for the heat recovery system: Building BL26 and Building BL27. For each building, a detailed study of the HVAC system is conducted, along with a comprehensive energy audit and performance assessment. For the building energy performance assessment, the RELAB app [21, 22] is used. The RELAB app is a software based on the EN ISO 52016 standard [23], where the building characteristics can be defined to estimate the energy demand. Based on the analysis, Building BL26 is chosen to host the heat recovery system.

The most straightforward approach for reusing waste heat from the server room is to transfer it to the building heating system via a water-to-water heat pump (WW-HP) to increase the heat temperature level. The heat recovery system will involve the installation of a heat exchanger in the outdoor plant area of Z3 and a heat pump on the roof of BL26. The heat exchanger will hydraulically separate the server room cooling system from the waste heat recovery system. The primary side of the heat exchanger will be connected to the cooling system in the server room while the secondary side will be connected to the heat pump of building BL26 heating system. A schematic representation of the waste heat recovery system and its connection to Z3 data centre and BL26 is displayed in Fig. 2.

Careful consideration must be given to selecting a water-to-water heat pump and integrating it into both the server room cooling system and the existing heating system. Indeed, the heat pump capacity is chosen in function of both the cooling load of the server room and the building peak heating demand. Since a heat pump heating capacity varies with source and sink temperatures, selection is based on performance at the required operating temperatures, rather than nominal capacity. The heat pump shall have an inlet temperature from the evaporator side of 15 °C and an outlet temperature from the evaporator side of 10 °C. The flow temperature in the system circuit of the BL26 shall be 58 °C while the return temperature shall be 50 °C. It is important that the heat pump model chosen for installation has good capacity control characteristics, so selecting multi-compressor models with 3–4 capacity stages is important to improve performance under partial load and offer scalability.

A preliminary analysis indicates that integrating a water-water heat pump into BL26 heating system could reduce natural gas consumption and lower overall energy costs by approximately 15%, while also decreasing CO₂ emissions by around 23%. The implications related to the waste heat recovery plant will be thoroughly discussed in a future work.

Fig. 2. Waste heat recovery plant scheme.

3 Building Digital Twin Environment Ongoing Development

The following chapters detail the architecture of the DT, with a focus on real-time data processing and the key features of the DT environment.

3.1 Real-Time Data Processing

In the Digital Twin architecture, the integration between physical devices and cloud-based analytics is essential for real-time monitoring and optimisation. The IoT HUB Service plays a central role in this process, enabling efficient data collection, transmission, and processing. It is an integrated service within IDP's DT platform, allowing the connection of physical devices with the cloud so that the data obtained by the devices or sensors can be visualised and consulted in real time from any type of client application that connects with the IoT HUB service through a web API. Physical devices equipped with sensors continuously capture operational parameters, which are then transmitted using protocols such as MQTT, AMQP, and HTTPS. The data is sent to an IoT HUB (Fig. 3), where it is processed and then forwarded to both a web API and an SQL database for analysis and storage. By structuring and storing sensor data in a centralised system, the Digital Twin can leverage it for simulation and predictive analysis, optimising system performance and enabling proactive decision-making.

One of the most relevant goals of a Digital Twin is to allow continuous and automatic system optimisation. This architecture ensures a continuous feedback loop between the physical and digital layers, enhancing operational efficiency, improving maintenance strategies, and supporting energy optimisation efforts.

Fig. 3. IoT HUB integration for real-time data processing in the DT architecture: schematic representation.

3.2 Digital Twin Environment Development

The development of a DT environment (Fig. 4) for data centre optimisation integrates real-time monitoring, simulation models, and predictive control mechanisms to enhance operational efficiency. The system collects real-time data on server room conditions, InRow cooling settings, chiller operations, and power supply performance. These data inputs are processed by the Simulation Model Tracking System (SMTS), along with the synthetic data generated by mathematical models (SIMBOTS), which simulate the behaviour of chillers, power supply systems, and the server room to provide a virtual representation of the physical infrastructure. A key component of this architecture is the Software-In-the-Loop Model Predictive Control (SiL-MPC) system, which employs predictive modelling and optimisation techniques to determine the most efficient control actions. By continuously optimising control trajectories throughout the year and incorporating forecasts of boundary conditions – such as weather data – the system enables more informed and energy efficient operational decisions. The SiL-MPC module processes current system data, simulates future states, and applies optimised control strategies to chillers, InRow cooling systems, and the overall server room environment. This continuous feedback loop ensures energy efficiency, stability, and proactive system optimisation, ultimately enhancing the reliability and performance of critical infrastructure in data centres.

Fig. 4. Data flow in the DT environment: Monitoring Data, Mathematical Models, SMTS and SiL-MPC schematisation.

An essential component of the DT environment is the dashboard, which serves as a centralised interface for visualizing and analysing data collected by the Simulation Model Tracking System (SMTS). The dashboard integrates multiple functionalities to enhance data analysis and decision-making. It includes a viewer, which offers an interactive 3D representation of the physical infrastructure, allowing users to navigate through the simulated environment. The monitoring section displays operational parameters, facilitating real-time assessment of performance. Additionally, the KPI section presents processed data in a graphical format, allowing to interpret the complex system behaviours. In particular, it can display performance metrics derived from simple monitoring data, such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) and Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER), providing valuable insights into energy efficiency and operational effectiveness. To further enhance collaboration, the shared documents section enables centralized document management, ensuring seamless access to relevant information.

4 Applications

4.1 Data Centre Digital Twin

The DT of the data centre environment relies on a set of measured, controlled, and simulated variables to optimise performance and energy efficiency. Sensors located in Z3 data centre measure several parameters that can be checked on EcoStruxure platform (by Schneider Electric) [24] – an infrastructure for cloud-connected digital services. These parameters concern the server room conditions, the InRow settings, the chillers settings, and the power supply system.

The data centre cooling system control variables are:

1. For the InRow cooling units:
 - a. room air setpoint temperature – from 18.0 °C to 32.2 °C;

- b. supply air setpoint temperature – from 15.0 °C to 30.2 °C;
- 2. For the chillers: supply water setpoint – from 7 °C to 13 °C.

Through simulations, the behaviour of chillers, the server room, and the power supply system will be reproduced. This will allow different management strategies to be tested without affecting regular data centre operations, enabling the identification of the most efficient solutions.

Data analysis and simulations are applied to various use cases, such as free cooling optimisation and InRow operation optimisation, both in terms of energy efficiency and acoustics. Indeed, in this specific project also acoustic comfort is considered because there are often system operators inside in person. The acoustic optimisation aspect is particularly relevant in cases where internal operators are present, ensuring a more comfortable working environment while maintaining optimal system performance. These efforts aim to reduce consumption, enhance sustainability, and ensure a more efficient operating environment for IT equipment. Figure 5 gives an overview of variables, models and use cases of the data centre DT.

Fig. 5. Overview of variables, models and use cases of the data centre DT.

The creation of a data centre DT could help to monitor room temperatures and cooling supply, prevent failures, and suggest efficient control strategies. As a result, it is expected to improve the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) by optimising room temperature settings and reducing cooling supply, leading to lower electricity expenses and CO₂ savings.

The Z3 cooling plant operation will be monitored as well, ensuring efficient performance, reducing failures, and improving control strategies. This approach is anticipated to lower the PUE by enhancing the plant overall efficiency, thereby cutting electricity costs, and contributing to CO₂ savings. Monitoring efforts will focus on the chiller operation mode – whether it is working in compression cooling, partial free cooling, or free cooling – along with the electricity consumption. Currently, free-cooling is activated only when the external temperature falls below 10 °C, which limits its utilisation. By integrating SIMBOTS for real-time simulation within the Software-in-the-Loop (SiL) environment, more advanced dynamic control strategies can be implemented. This approach enables the extension of free cooling operation across a broader range of conditions, enhancing its overall contribution to energy savings.

4.2 Active Heat Recovery Digital Twin

The heat recovery DT should be designed to monitor, control, and simulate the operation of the WW-HP integrated to BL26 existing heating system. To ensure efficient operation, several key variables are measured, including the electricity consumption of the WW-HP, water temperatures, and water flow rates. These parameters provide essential insights into system performance and energy usage. Control strategies focus on adjusting the WW-HP temperature setpoints and operation modes, as well as regulating flow rates or temperature differences (ΔT). Simulations could focus on a physics-based and/or data-driven BL26 model to estimate the heating needs and on a WW-HP model to study the system behaviour under different conditions.

The main use cases include integrating the WW-HP into the existing heating plant, optimising system management during mid-seasons, and implementing free cooling strategies to enhance energy efficiency. A key challenge is the non-trivial coupling of the WW-HP with the existing system, requiring careful analysis of energy flows. During mid-seasons, when the data centre needs to dissipate more energy than the BL26 requires, the WW-HP will operate alongside the Z3 chillers to balance the load. In winter conditions, the WW-HP will work in synergy with the free cooling mode of the Z3 chillers, further improving overall efficiency. Figure 6 gives an overview of variables, models and use cases of the heat recovery DT.

Fig. 6. Overview of variables, models and use cases of the heat recovery DT.

The water-water heat pump extracts waste heat from the server room and integrates it into the existing gas boiler heating system of building BL26. The main objective of the heat recovery DT is to verify the correct integration of the water-to-water heat exchange system, ensuring that the control strategy prioritizes heat pump operation. At the same time, it is essential to monitor the electricity consumption of both the heat pumps and the circulation pumps, as well as to evaluate the thermal energy effectively produced. Another key aspect is the analysis of the building heating needs and the performance of the heat pump, with the goal of optimising system efficiency and minimizing overall energy costs. To achieve this, it is necessary to track key parameters such as supply and return temperatures, water flow rates at the evaporator and condenser, and water temperatures at various points in the system. Finally, based on the collected data, the system should be able to suggest optimal control variable trajectories, thereby maximizing overall efficiency.

5 Conclusions

The paper presents a brief introduction to HYCOOL-IT project, with a description of data centre Z3 and its WHR system. The implementation of a WHR system in the Z3 data centre, using a WW-HP connected to the heating system of Building BL26, will enable a significant reduction in natural gas consumption, energy costs, and CO₂ emissions, while simultaneously improving the overall energy efficiency of the campus. To ensure correct management and optimisation of the system, a DT environment is currently under development. This article outlines its general architecture, emphasising the crucial role of integrating physical devices with cloud-based analytics for real-time monitoring and optimisation. At the core of this process is the IoT HUB service, which facilitates efficient data collection, transmission, and processing, enabling smarter and more proactive system management. By combining real-time monitoring, simulation models, and predictive control, the DT continuously optimises data centre operations. Leveraging predictive modelling and optimisation techniques, it enhances energy efficiency, stability, and the overall reliability of critical data centre infrastructure. The creation of two DTs – the data centre DT and the Active (WW-HP) Heat Recovery DT – could be an effective approach for managing energy use, controlling key variables, and testing different management strategies without disrupting normal operations. By continuously monitoring and adjusting parameters such as temperature setpoints, cooling settings, and flow rates, the DTs will help to enhance overall performance, improve PUE, and reduce energy costs and CO₂ emissions. Looking ahead, the integration of the WW-HP system with the BL26 existing heating system represents an innovative approach to coupling data centre operations with building energy needs. The simulations and real-time data analysis will enable further optimisation, particularly during mid-seasons and winter when energy efficiency is critical. The expected outcomes will not only contribute to lowering operational costs but will also provide valuable insights into the broader application of DT technology in industrial settings, paving the way for more sustainable and efficient energy management practices across similar infrastructures. As the project progresses and more mature results become available, original findings and novel contributions are expected to be presented in future publications.

Acknowledgements. HYCOOL-IT project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program under Grant Agreement No. 101138623 and is scheduled to run from December 1, 2023, to November 30, 2026.

References

1. Grieves, M.: Origins of the Digital Twin Concept (2016). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26367.61609>
2. Opoku, D.G.J., Perera, S., Osei-Kyei, R., Rashidi, M.: Digital twin application in the construction industry: a literature review. *J. Build. Eng.* **40**, 102726 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JOBE.2021.102726>
3. Abdelrahman, M., Macatulad, E., Lei, B., Quintana, M., Miller, C., Biljecki, F.: What is a digital twin anyway? Deriving the definition for the built environment from over 15,000

- scientific publications. *Build. Environ.* **274**, 112748 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2025.112748>
4. Ozturk, G.B.: Digital twin research in the AECO-FM industry. *J. Build. Eng.* **40**, 102730 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102730>
 5. Boje, C., Guerriero, A., Kubicki, S., Rezgui, Y.: Towards a semantic construction digital twin: directions for future research. *Autom. Constr.* **114**, 103179 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AUTCON.2020.103179>
 6. Sphere BIM Digital Twin Platform - White Paper Q4: Digital Twin Definitions for Buildings - How to Move Digital Twin Environments to the AECO Sector (2019). [Online]. www.sphere-project.eu
 7. Singh, M., Fuenmayor, E., Hinchy, E.P., Qiao, Y., Murray, N., Devine, D.: Digital Twin: Origin to Future. DPI AG (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/asi4020036>
 8. AlBalkhy, W., Karmaoui, D., Ducoulombier, L., Lafhaj, Z., Linner, T.: Digital twins in the built environment: definition, applications, and challenges. *Autom. Constr.* **162**, 105368 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AUTCON.2024.105368>
 9. European Committee for Standardization: DRAFT prEN 18162 Building Information Modelling (BIM) - Digital twins applied to the built environment - Concept and definitions (2025) [Online]. www.bsigroup.com
 10. Bortolini, R., Rodrigues, R., Alavi, H., Vecchia, L.F.D., Forcada, N.: Digital Twins' Applications for Building Energy Efficiency: A Review. *MDPI* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15197002>
 11. Liu, Z., Li, M., Ji, W.: Development and application of a digital twin model for Net zero energy building operation and maintenance utilizing BIM-IoT integration. *Energy Build* **328**, 115170 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2024.115170>
 12. Lu, Q., Xie, X., Parlikad, A.K., Schooling, J.M.: Digital twin-enabled anomaly detection for built asset monitoring in operation and maintenance. *Autom. Constr.* **118**, 103277 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AUTCON.2020.103277>
 13. Zhao, J., Feng, H., Chen, Q., Garcia de Soto, B.: Developing a conceptual framework for the application of digital twin technologies to revamp building operation and maintenance processes. *J. Build. Eng.* **49**, 104028 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2022.104028>
 14. Elshabshiri, A., Ghanim, A., Hussien, A., Maksoud, A., Mushtaha, E.: Integration of building information modeling and digital twins in the operation and maintenance of a building lifecycle: a bibliometric analysis review. *J. Build. Eng.* **99**, 111541 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JOBE.2024.111541>
 15. Cespedes-Cubides, A.S., Jradi, M.: A Review of Building Digital Twins to Improve Energy Efficiency in the Building Operational Stage. *Springer Nature* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42162-024-00313-7>
 16. Seghezzi, E., et al.: Towards an occupancy-oriented digital twin for facility management: test campaign and sensors assessment. *Appl. Sci. (Switz.)* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11073108>
 17. Arowoia, V.A., Moehler, R.C., Fang, Y.: Digital twin technology for thermal comfort and energy efficiency in buildings: a state-of-the-art and future directions. *Energy Built Environ.* **5**(5), 641–656 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBENV.2023.05.004>
 18. Yuan, X., Liang, Y., Hu, X., Xu, Y., Chen, Y., Kosonen, R.: Waste heat recoveries in data centers: a review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **188**, 113777 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2023.113777>
 19. IDP Ingeniería y Arquitectura Iberia SL. <https://www.idp.es/en/idp-digital/>. last accessed 08 Apr 2025
 20. Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI). <https://fmi-standard.org/>. last accessed 08 Apr 2025

21. Romagnosi, M., Aprile, M., Dénarié, A.: Energy and economic simulation of a renewable energy community applied to a new generation ultra-low temperature district heating and cooling network. In: E3S Web of Conferences. EDP Sciences (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202452305003>
22. Famiglietti, J., Aprile, M., Spirito, G., Motta, M.: Net-Zero climate emissions districts: potentials and constraints for social housing in Milan. *Energies (Basel)* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031504>
23. ISO 52016-1:2017 - Energy performance of buildings - Energy needs for heating and cooling, internal temperatures and sensible and latent heat loads - Part 1: Calculation procedures, ISO 52016-1:2017 (2017)
24. EcoStruxure Platform by Schneider Electric. <https://www.se.com/it/it/work/campaign/innovation/platform.jsp>. last accessed 08 Apr 2025

Open Access This chapter is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license and indicate if changes were made.

The images or other third party material in this chapter are included in the chapter's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the chapter's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder.

